

STUDENTS' NEEDS IN LEARNING ENGLISH FOR PHARMACY

Djalilova Dildora¹, Ashurova Nigora²

Teacher of Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute

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Annatation: The aim of this paper is to provide details on the importance of teaching language course to Pharmacy students, to present some published resources and coursebooks that language instructors in Pharmacy schools could use and, on the practical side, to present a useful application which helps students refresh and strengthen their knowledge of drug names' orthography. The methods of research that we have used are primary and secondary source analysis and the comparative method.

Keywords: ESL, ESP, pharmaceutical terminology, communication, language teaching

INTRODUCTION

In 1937, Professor Adelaide E. Harris was describing in one of the first academic studies in teaching English to Pharmacy students how on the door leading to the School of Pharmacy of her university were two gold lettered words, which sometimes surprised the passers-by: "Pharmacognosy. English". At present, it has become clear that the successful teaching of specialized terminology in English is of utmost importance in the case of medical professionals whose day-to-day activities include interaction with patients and/or with other medical staff with whom they communicate in English. This not only includes pharmacists, but also doctors, dentists, nurses, veterinarians, orderlies, health assistant and consultants, pharmacy assistants, pharmacy and dental technicians and laboratory technicians, etc. In today's globalized society most communication at high levels is carried out in English, especially in the medical field where a large part of the patients as well as staff do not share the same cultural and linguistic background.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

English for the Pharmaceutical Industry is probably the most useful resource on the market at the moment for Pharmacy students of at least an intermediate level. The authors mention that their book is designed to "equip learners with the linguistic skills and specialist vocabulary necessary to understand daily situations in a work environment" (Bücheler et al. 2010, 4) and, after three years of using this book with second year Pharmacy students we can opionate that it is one of the most professional and helpful resource an educator could wish for, with

excellent recordings that not only help boost students' knowledge in pharmaceutical terminology but also help introduce the learner to the specific culture and climate of the corporate pharmaceuticals. The only downside to using it is that this exceptional learning tool is that it is not very extensive, as it includes only six chapters with an additional final test unit and partner dialogues, useful phrases, listening extracts, and an A-Z wordlist .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

English for Pharmacy Writing and Oral Communication is much more extensive but generally less interactive yet a lot denser in terminology related to anatomy and exercises. It is most practically used by students who have attained at least an intermediate level of English and it stands out among other resources due to its rich collection of pharmacy dialogues, which are thematically organized to match the chapters of the book. No other coursebook or language book for pharmacists can boast such a wealth of over 60 pages of pharmacy dialogues categorized according to anatomical components (for instance, mouth and nose, urinary system, ears and eyes, etc.). An interesting aspect of this workbook is that the author offers direct advice to speakers of some nationalities as regards the pronunciation difficulties they might face when speaking English.

English for Pharmacy and Parapharmacy is a useful coursebook for students whose English language level is below intermediate. Beside vocabulary exercises on topics such as "Sanitary products", "Phytotherapy" or "Dermopharmacy" (subjects which are not commonly tackled in other such manuals), it also teaches beginner-level grammar ("Present simple", "There is, There are", "Present Continuous", etc.) and writing exercises ("Describing yourself", "Elaborate your diet", etc.). Appendices include a list of verbs and a vocabulary. The number of applications could be greater, some pages contain no exercises at all (only broad text for reading exercises with no rubric or just diagrams) and there are usually only two exercises per page (some with few test items or questions).

From the point of view of teaching content, many study resources, including the ones presented in the first part of this study, offer topics more connected to medical terminology in general (e.g. the digestive system, herbal remedies, drugs, vitamins, nutrition, the cardiovascular system, etc.). A topic which is less covered and which would greatly benefit future pharmacists may be the study of the orthography of drug names and drug nomenclature (more exactly, their capitalization). Students should be reminded that pharmacists, pharmacy assistant and technicians are sometimes quizzed at interviews by possible employers on distinguishing generical, chemical or brand names of drugs, which represents a fundamental skill for the profession (Winnipeg College 2008). It is

therefore important to mark the difference between different drug denominations :

-the chemical name (most students would remember from their high school chemistry lessons that for chemical nomenclature they should refer to the IUPAC names); the difficulty brought by the use of chemical names in an English course for Pharmacy students is that chemical names tend to be rather long and complex, even for well known drugs such as ibuprofen, i.e. (RS)-2-(4-(2-methylpropyl)phenyl)propanoic acid; bearing this in mind, from a pedagogical point of view it would be sensible to avoid using or testing chemical drug names in the English classroom, yet the students should be informed what chemical denomination is and how to recognize it, and could benefit from exercising the spelling out chemical names;

-the nonproprietary or generic name usually indicates through a suffix or prefix to what category the drug belongs. For example, acyclovir presents the “-vir” suffix which is specific to antiviral medications. The generic name may be different from country to country.

CONCLUSION

As the previously mentioned authors points out, writing something down does not guarantee getting a message across from one person to another (Albert 2000, 26) The exigencies of medical writing have grown in accordance with the recent development in the pharmaceutical field and with the arrival of stricter regulation of clinical trials documents, case reports, investigation brochures, patient consent forms, research protocols, and regulatory documents in general. There are also emerging subdomains of medical writing such as marketing focused writing or medical journalism writing.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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